

INDIAN FRANKINCENSE:AN INSIGHT INTO *BOSWELLIA SERRATA* WITH ITS PHARMACOLOGICAL EFFECT

Shreya Ranjan*, Ankita Pokhriyal, Pranshu Tangri

*GRD(PG) IMT, Department of pharmaceutical sciences, Rajpur road, Dehradun,
248001, India*

**Corresponding author: shreyaranjan321@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

The present review is based on the medicinally useful plant *Boswellia serrata*, which a member of the Burseraceae family and is sometimes referred as salai, salai guggul, or Indian frankincense. 60–80% of the resin and 5-9% of the essential oils of *Boswellia serrata* are convertible in chemical solvents, while the remaining 6-30% comprises of polysaccharides. In Salai guggul, the fibrous fraction mostly consists of pentose and hexose sugars, but the resin fraction is abundant in boswellic acids and its crucial oils, which are composed of various polyterpenes. Boswellic acid, which is the collective name for the *Boswellia* species, offers beneficial biological qualities like anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antibacterial, antiarthritic, anticancer, anti-diarrheal action, hypolipidemic activity, immunomodulatory activity, hepatoprotective effects, antiasthmatic effect, antidiabetic effect and diuretic activity, among others. Boswellic acid has been discovered to be a new, strong, and targeted anti-inflammatory medicine because it inhibits the 5-lipoxygenase enzyme non-redoxically. It also targets the enzymes topoisomerase, angiogenesis, and cytochrome p450. Regarding the pharmacological profile of *B. serrata* and the prevailing level of knowledge about the species, this overview is a genuine effort to explore and characterize the situation.

Keywords: *Boswellia serrata*, 5-lipoxygenase, Boswellic acid, Indian frankincense

INTRODUCTION

Other name: Salai/Salai guggul

Family: Burseraceae

Genus: *Boswellia*

Frankincense is one of the prevalent used ingredient in conventional herbal remedies [1]. The phrase "frankincense" is originates from the ancient French expression "franc encens" which meaning "pure incense" and "pure or noble high-quality incense" [2]. This tree, which has moderate to substantial branches, is found in barren mountain regions of the Near East, northern Africa, and India [3,4]. It is frequently referred to as salai guggul, loban, kundru, or Indian olibanum [5]. With 17 genera and 600 species, the Burseraceae family is represented in the plant kingdom and is found throughout all tropical climates. The Genus *Boswellia* is known to have about 25 species, most of which are located in the Arabian Peninsula, India, and the northeast

African coast. The designation of 3 of these species as "authentic Frankincense-producing trees" dates back to ancient times. [6,7].

Boswellia carterii, which is native to East Africa and China, is called "moxor," and the sticky substance that it generates is known as "lubandhakar." *Boswellia frereana*, which is native to Northeast Africa (Somalia), referred to as "jagcaar," and the sticky substance it produces called as "lobanmajdi" or "maydi." Additionally, *Boswellia sacra* fleuck, which is indigenous to

the Middle East and South Arabia, is termed in Arabic as "maghrayt d' sheehaz," and the sticky material it produces called "lubandhakar" [8,9,10]. The genus *Boswellia* has approximately 30 varieties and typically located in drought-prone regions of South Asia, the Arabia or tropical Africa [11], whereas morning mist provides humidity. For example The Arabian Peninsula is home to *Boswellia sacra*, Ethiopia to *Boswellia papyrifera* (Caill. ex Delile) Hochst. and *Boswellia riviae* Engl., Eritrea to *Boswellia neglecta* S. Moore, and North Africa, Somalia to *Boswellia carterii* and *Boswellia frereana* Birdw. But the most common sources of frankincense are *B. frereana*, *B. sacra*, *B. papyrifera*, and *B. serrata*, that can be located in Somalia, Yemen, Oman, India, and Pakistan [12].

Fig.1: Tree of *Boswellia Serrata*[87]

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF INDIAN FRANKINCENSE

The deciduous tree *B. serrata* typically reaches a moderate height of 4–5 meters. Identical to other branching trees of medium to big size, its circumference is 2.4 m, with an average of 1.5 m. The delicate outer peel is readily peeled off and changes color from greenish gray, crimson to ash or golden. Upon detached or cutting, the papery layer releases transparent pieces, tears, or sticky oil droplets that range in color from white to yellow [13]. The gum has a bitter taste and a balsamic scent.

Leaves	Strange pinnate, Ex-stipulate and morphologically varied, and clustered around the branches' extremities, length: 30 to 45 cm
Leaflets	Numerous, oblong or ovate-lanceolate, rounded base, 2.5–6.3 × 1.2–3.0 cm, practically sessile, short-toothed, primarily pubescent, 8–15 in number.
Flowers	Small, white, bisexual, and found in panicles or axillary racemes at the tips of branches.
Petals	White-pink oblong-ovate, 0.5–0.8 cm, with a disk at the base
Fruits	1.25 cm long, trigonous, oblong, cotyledous, trifid

Fig. 2: *B. serrata* leaves or resin [88]

COMPOSITION OF INDIAN FRANKINCENSE

A wide variety of chemicals are present in different species of *Boswellia* [14]. Depending on the weather, harvest circumstances, and location location, the crucial oil and other compounds' composition varies from species to another species [14,15]. According to reports, frankincense contains 5-9% crucial oil, 6-30% gums (a combination of carbohydrates), and 60-85% sticky substances (mixtures of terpenes) [16].

Fig. 3: Composition of *B. serrata*

Monoterpenes (α -thujene), diterpenes (macrocyclic diterpenoids like incensole, incensole oxide, iso-incensole oxide, and a diterpene alcohol [serratol]), triterpenes (like α - and β -amyryns), pentacyclic triterpenic acids (boswellic acids), and tetracyclic triterpenic acids (tirucall-8,24-dien-21-oic acids) are all present in the resinous portion of *Boswellia serrata* [17–23]. However, the former are thought to be primarily in charge of its pharmacological effects [24,25].

BA is equivalent to 3-hydroxyurs-12-ene-23-oic acid chemically. A knownelement of chemistry shared by all plants in the genus *Boswellia* is the presence of Boswellic acids. All *Boswellia* species include the six main BAs, though in different amounts: α and β -Boswellic Acids (BA, 10–21%), Acetylated α and β -BAs (ABA, 0.05–6%), 11-keto- β -Boswellic acid (KBA, 2.5–7.5%), and 3-O-acetyl-11-keto- β -Boswellic acid (AKBA, 0.1–3%) [26]. The 2 best powerful, effective, and favorable drugs for alleviating inflammationamong all of *Boswellia*'s BAs are AKBA and KBA.

A limited amount of diterpenes and monoterpenoids (pinene, cis-verbenol, trans-pinocarveol, borneol, myrcene, phallendrene, cadinene, verbenone, limonene, thuja-2,4(10)-diene, and p-cymene) are present in Salai guggal essential oil. Monoterpenoids are primarily composed of α -pinene (73.3%) [27].

MECHANISM OF ACTION

The active possible objectives of BAs are focused on 5-Lipooxygenase, angiogenesis, topoisomerases, and the cytochrome p450 enzyme [28–31].

Fig.4: Mechanism of action

5-LO Suppression

Leukotrienes and 5-hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid are the main products of 5-LO's conversion of endogenous arachidonic acid in neutrophils. It causes chemotherapy, increased penetration, airway obstruction, and blood vessel constriction. BA is a distinctive targeted, and non-redox

inhibitor of 5-LO since it does not degrade the characteristics of cyclooxygenase and 12-lipoxygenase enzymes, neither does it decrease arachidonic acid peroxidation [28–41].

Topoisomerases

BAs inhibit human topoisomerase (I and II α) with dual catalytic activity. BAs interact with DNA for binding, which suppresses DNA synthesis and topoisomerase (I and II α) in human leukemia promyelocytic cells in a dose-responsive manner [28, 36-39].

Erythrocyte elastase suppression

Elastase from human leukocytes reduces lung flexibility, narrowing the airways, interferes with mucous secretion in the lungs, and reduces mucus evacuation. BAs inhibit the action of the elastase from human leukocytes, that results in pulmonary disorder [39].

Suppression of C2 convertase

Boswellic acid restrict the enzyme C2 convertase, that performs the essential activity in the conventional complement system for particular antibodies. The classical complement system supports specific immunity because only certain kinds of antibodies are irresponsive to antigen stimuli and can activate the mechanism [40].

PHARMACOLOGICAL EFFECT OF BOSWELLIA SERRATA

Anti-inflammatory Effect

In general, higher species have evolved inflammation as a defense mechanism in reaction to harmful assaults such as tissue damage, microbial infection, and other unpleasant situations. It is a vital host immunological response that permits the elimination of toxic stimuli and the repair of injured tissue [42], which is typified by discomfort, edema, inflammation, and occasionally lack of activity [14].

The body's cells produce little facilitator molecules called leukotrienes. They can lead to inflammation by encouraging autoimmune reactions, cell adhesion, free radical damage, and cell migration to the inflammatory position. Leukotrienes have been linked to a number of inflammatory conditions, such as psoriasis, rheumatism, arthritis, colitis, and asthma. [43]

Boswellia has been demonstrated to be a particular leukotriene inhibitor. It works by preventing the production of leukotrienes, which in turn reduces inflammation and shrinks the inflammatory tissue that is often the main source of pain and suffering [43]. It's believed that boswellic acids are the biologically active components of *salai* that give its anti-tumorogenic and therapeutic activity, according to data from in vitro and in vivo experiments. Frankincense has demonstrated efficacy for dealing with a various type of inflammatory disorders [44]. According to a study, patients with plaque-induced mouth disorders saw less periodontal swelling because to the anti-inflammatory characteristics of frankincense powder and the extracted substances [45].

Analgesic Effect

According to studies, *B. serrata* extract evens fair skin tone and lessens skin irritation and redness [46]. Frankincense was applied to wounds and used to alleviate rheumatism in India. It was a component of a number of skin treatments in China, such as those for infected wounds and bruises, and as a result, a leprosy therapy [47].

Extracts from the *Boswellia* family of plants have been shown to have a calming impact on itchy skin because of the pentacyclic triterpene (steroid-like) structure that is shared by different boswellic acid contents [46]. Boswellic acid sheds some information on how it works, which appears to be different from that of steroidal medications and aspirin [48].

In order to be readily incorporated into compositions that can be used on skin or hair and to enhance the stability of products that contain the extract, *Boswellia* extracts that contain boswellic acid and its derivatives must be dissolved or spread out in a suitable carrier, such as lipid alcohols or saturated fats [46]. Furthermore, Alpha-keto BA is considered to be a successful externally applied treatment for relaxing the skin and reducing wrinkles on the face [49].

Antimicrobial Effect

The crucial oil extracted from *B. carterii*'s oleogum substances has been shown to exhibit antibacterial properties against a variety of microbes, such as gram-positive and negative bacterial strains and fungus [50].

A study that examined the antimicrobial properties of boswellic acids in vitro employed clinically significant gram-positive and negative bacterial strains. AKBA was the most effective boswellic acid at inhibiting bacterial pathogens. However, only gram-positive bacteria were susceptible to AKBA's action. Gram-negative bacteria may be resistant to lipophilic AKBA because of the presence of a hydrophilic exterior wall, which is mostly comprised of polysaccharide molecules and forms a hydrophilic permeability obstacle that guards against the effects of hydrophobic chemicals. [51].

Bacterial cells form multilayered communities called biofilms. It is well known that *Staphylococci* can create hard-to-break biofilms on injured tissues or implanted medical devices. Biofilm infections are difficult to cure since they are resistant to antibiotics by nature. According to report, AKBA efficiently prevent the staphylococcal biofilm and decreased the amount of biofilm that these bacterial parasites produced. This study shown that AKBA can both prevent and lessen the production of biofilms by *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. The effective substance opposed all of the gram-positive bacterial parasites that were assessed was AKBA [51].

The antibacterial properties of boswellic acid molecules were investigated against infections that affect the oral cavity. According to the experiment's findings, AKBA is the most effective antibacterial substance against every bacterium examined [15]. AKBA can be used to generate an antimicrobial substance against bacteria found in the mouth and to prepare mouthwash to avoid and cure infection in the mouth [52].

Antiarthritic activity

BA's efficacy in treating rabbit arthritis induced by bovine serum albumin (BSA) is being investigated. Oral BA administration at daily doses of 25, 50, and 100 mg per kg significantly

lower erythrocytes in knees with BSA, altering the synovial fluid protein's electrophoretic pattern [53]. An extract of salai-guggal has been demonstrated to have antiarthritic properties and to significantly reduce edema in rats or mice generated by carrageenan or dextran [54]. Many more research targeting the anti-arthritis properties of BAs were subsequently carried out. In animals with adjuvant-induced arthritis, the consumption of BAs or frankincense improved lysosomal stability and decreased glucuronidase activity [55]. Additionally, in rats with adjuvant-induced arthritis, the levels of connective tissue metabolites in their urine decreased, mostly during the chronic phase but only slightly during the acute phase [56].

The effectiveness of *Boswellia serrata* was assessed in a placebo-controlled experiment involving 42 individuals suffering from osteoarthritis because of the positive outcomes of several animal experimental experiments [57]. A statistically significant and clinically relevant increase in walking distance, increased knee flexion, and decreased knee discomfort were reported by all patients undergoing medication treatment. The frequency of knee joint swelling was reduced. In conclusion, these investigations demonstrate that BAs have anti-inflammatory (mostly anti-arthritis) properties in vivo [58].

Anticancer activity

BSE was recently reported to prevent the spread of brain tumors and breast carcinoma. In mice, BSE, which contains 60% BAs, appears to have suppressed tumor growth and inflammation. Through disruption of DNA, RNA, and protein production, antineoplastic effects have been studied in mice with Ehrlich ascites carcinoma and S-180 tumors, resulting in inhibition of cell growth. By increasing the bioavailability of AKBA, BSE's effectiveness against peritumoral edema can be increased [26].

B. serrata demonstrated anticancer effects on a numerous number of tumor cells, including those were located in liver, brain, prostate, intestine, or leukocytes. AKBA was found to have an inhibitory effect on NF- κ B and to promote angiogenesis and death in neoplastic cells via activating transcription 3-related pathways and the signaling transducer pathway [38,59-64].

Antidiarrheal activity

B. serrata extract helps individuals with inflammatory bowel syndrome manage their diarrhea without making them constipated. It regulates diarrhea brought on by acetylcholine and BaCl₂ by preventing smooth muscle contraction in the intestines [65].

Hypolipidemic property

Water-soluble component of *B. serrata* extract demonstrated its hypolipidemic potential by increasing HDL and decreasing total cholesterol (38–48%) in rats given an atherogenic diet [66]. Mice with endotoxin/galactosamine-induced liver injury show hepatoprotection from alcoholic extract of salai guggul (AESG), as seen by decreased blood enzyme, aminotransferase, SGOT, and SGPT titres [67]. When animals consume a diet that contains saturated fat and cholesterol, salai gum holds their blood cholesterol and triglyceride levels within an ideal range [68].

Immunomodulatory activity

Numerous research have examined the immunological toxicological aspects of BA as well as the humoral and cell-mediated components of the immune system [69]. According to a thorough investigation of the structural requirements for BAs, AKBA has the most inhibitory action against 5-LO among the six acids [70]. Using rats as antest model of inflammatory arthropathy, this provided support for additional studies on the immunological and anti-inflammatory arthropathy effects of Boswellic acid, which is made from the sticky material of *Boswellia serrata* (*B. serrata*), in carrageenan-induced paw edema and adjuvant-induced arthritis[71].

The specific immunological role of BA and its corresponding role of action were sought to be elucidated by further in vitro and in vivo experiments. When mice were challenged with the sheep red blood cell antigen, the biopolymeric fraction (BOS 200) from *B. serrata* caused a delayed hypersensitive reaction due to immunostimulatory effects, as seen by the dose-dependent increase in footpad thickness. It was also noted that the immunoglobulins IgG and IgM antibody titer increased, reaching its maximum at the maxima dose of BOS 200 (10 mg per kg). The phagocytic function was enhanced by incubating macrophages with BOS 200, as evidenced by the noticeably elevated phagocytic index. After BOS 200 was administered, splenic lymphocyte immunophenotyping showed a substantial rise in CD4 and CD8. Additionally, TNF- α , IFN- γ , and IL-4 levels in the serum were markedly elevated following oral treatment of *Boswellia Serrata* 200 at 3 and 10 mg per kg [72].

The possible immunomodulatory effects of 7 standard extracts of *Boswellia serrata* sticky material (65% BA). The results of this investigation showed that, when evaluated using the in vitro CFDA-SE assay, The extracts from salai guggal did not promote the growth of B cells or lymphocytes without an activator. When one of the *Boswellia* extracts without an activator was added, there was a noticeable increase in FOXP3 and regulatory T (Treg) cells, which are proteins involved in immune system response. This demonstrated BA's immunostimulant potential[73].

Hepatoprotective effects

Preclinical research showed that BA has a hepatoprotective effect on various hepatotoxicity models by addressing oxidative stress, inflammatory, and apoptotic factors. A well-known cyanide that causes hepatotoxicity in animals is carbon tetrachloride. The protective properties of *Boswellia serrata* colophony against rat liver cirrhosis caused by carbon tetrachloride. In order to reduce inflammation and oxidative stress in the liver, the gum resin mediated hepatoprotection by increasing the catalase activity and the liver's antioxidant capability, as well as by decreasing lipid peroxidation and the production of NF κ B, TNF- α , IL-6, and kidney transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β) [74].

Most likely, the suppression of 5-LO activity provided the hepatoprotection [75]. Oxidative stress, cytokine imbalance, and insulin resistance are all strongly associated with NAFLD. A three-month high-fat diet (HFD) was used to induce liver steatosis or inflammation (NFLD) in rats, as evidenced by a deviation in the main liver biomarkers. Rats administered pioglitazone or The insulin sensitivity of BAs (125 or 250 mg/kg) was better than that of the control groups

well as decreased liver index, liver enzyme activity, serum TNF- α and IL-6, and liver iNOS expression. There is strong evidence from this investigation that Boswellic acids have ability for the clinical assessment of NAFLD [76].

Antidiabetic effect and diuretic activity

Olibanum gum resin has long been used to treat diabetes in individuals and has been shown to have positive benefits on a wide range of illnesses. Additionally, a double-blind clinical experiment including 71 patients was conducted to compare the effectiveness of guggal resin and a placebo in treatment of diabetes mellitus. According to their findings, olibanum gum resin reduces blood serum level, hexose, HbA1c, fatty acids and enhances glycemic management [77].

In experimental albino rats, an aqueous extract made from *Boswellia serrata* Roxb. oleo gum at a concentration of 50 mg per kg had notable diuretic action. When consumed intraperitoneally, the water-based extract exhibited natriuretic or kaliuretic actions, which increased urine production. Additionally, at 3000 mg/kg body weight, the extract showed no signs of severe toxicity [78].

Anti asthmatic effect

Boswellia has long been considered an effective treatment and is well-known for its breathing-related effects. It has been used to cure cough, catarrh, bronchitis, and asthma in massages, steam inhalations, and baths. By inhibiting the formation of leukotrienes, Boswellic acids, thertepenoids found in *Boswellia serrata*, lower and prevent inflammation in a variety of chronic inflammatory illnesses, including asthma. Numerous investigations have shown that the alcohol extract of Salai guggal (AESG) has anti-asthmatic properties in individuals with an extended background of asthma because it stimulates MAPK, mobilizes intracellular Ca²⁺, and inhibits the formation of leukotrienes [79].

BA's antiasthmatic potential and its effects in an asthma induced mice were investigated. They discovered that the animal administered with BA might reduce allergy inflammation. They discovered that the BA-treated animals were able to decrease the production of Th2 cytokines, ovalbumin-specific IgE, allergic inflammation, and hyperresponsiveness [80]. BA was shown to reduce lung structure damage, slow down cell infiltration, and attenuate fibrotic lungs by 5-LO inhibitory action in a laboratory model of pulmonary fibrosis using bleomycin [81].

Dosage

Usually, *Boswellia* is consumed as a tablet, capsule, or bark infusion. *Boswellia* products come in a wide range of varieties, making it challenging to standardize them. The recommended amount of *Boswellia* is often consumed as a tablet, capsule, or bark infusion for inflammatory or asthmatic disorders is 300 to 400 mg three times a day of the suitable extract, which contains 60% BAs [82].

Safety and toxicity

Boswellia has exceptionally low toxicity, and unlike many anti-inflammatory chemical medications, its anti-inflammatory actions do not negatively affect breathing, heart rhythm,

arterial pressure, or other sensory responses[83]. As one of the safe substances, boswellia gum resin has obtained certification approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (USFDA) for use as a food additive [52].

BAs have been shown to be safe in models that are acute, subacute, and chronic. *B. serrata* rarely exhibits signs of toxicity or serious adverse effects ($LD_{50} > 2 \text{ g/kg}$). These adverse effects include skin rashes, urticaria, nausea, and very minor gastrointestinal distress (diarrhea). Topical use of *B. serrata* extract may result in mild adverse effect, contact dermatitis [84–86]. When compared to the negative effects of contemporary medications, frankincense's side effects are comparatively mild and unimportant. Therefore, when used at the recommended and therapeutic amounts, it can be regarded as quite safe.

CONCLUSION

The current review centers on the scientific acknowledgement of *B. serrata*'s therapeutic function and activity, which was historically employed in religious and cultural rituals but is today prized for its many positive medicinal properties. Both conventional and contemporary natural medicine have utilized frankincense to cure a wide range of ailments with few detrimental effects. Boswellic acids are the medicinal plant-based constituents that shown encouraging outcomes in a number of laboratorial and experimental investigations. Its therapeutic qualities are also well known, mostly for the treatment of inflammatory illnesses, wound healing, and its antibacterial action in some malignant diseases.

Boswellia serrata is a useful tree, particularly because of the gum that it secretes from its stem. Pharmacological research has been done on gum that is used to treat a variety of illnesses. The stem, root, and leaves of plants may potentially contain a valuable element and continue to be a suitable area for future research. Even though *Boswellia* has archival, historic, theological, cultural, and pharmacological contexts, it has not been extensively explored, and there are still differences among what we know about its traditional use and the scientific information that is currently accessible.

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